

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm Five

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁰ For the choir director; for flute accompaniment. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psalm 5:1 לְמִנְצַחַת אֶל־הַנְּחִילוֹת מִזְמוֹר</p>
<p>¹ Give ear to my words, O LORD, Consider my groaning.</p>	<p>לְדָוִד : ² אֲמַרְי הַאֲזִינָה אִיהוָה</p>
<p>² Heed the sound of my cry for help, my King and my God, For to You I pray.</p>	<p>בִּינָה הִגִּינִי : ³ הַקְּשִׁיבָה וְלִקְוֹל שׁוֹעֵי מִלְכִי וְאֱלֹהֵי כִּי־אֵלַיךָ</p>
<p>³ In the morning, O LORD, You will hear my voice; In the morning I will order <i>my prayer</i> to You and <i>eagerly</i> watch.</p>	<p>אֶתְפַּלֵּל : ⁴ אִיהוָה בִּקְרָה תִשְׁמַע קוֹלִי בִּקְרָה אֶעֱרֹךְ־לְךָ וְאַצְפֶּה : ⁵ כִּי אֵלֹהִים</p>
<p>⁴ For You are not a God who takes pleasure in wickedness; No evil dwells with You.</p>	<p>אֶל־חַפְצֵי רָשָׁע וְאַתָּה לֹא יִגְדַּךְ רָע : ⁶ לֹא־יִתְיַצְּבוּ הוֹלְלִים לְנֶגְדְךָ</p>
<p>⁵ The boastful shall not stand before Your eyes; You hate all who do iniquity.</p>	<p>עֵינֶיךָ שָׁנְאֶת כָּל־פֹּעֵלֵי אָוֶן : ⁷ תִּאבְדֹּר הַבְּרִי כָזֹב אִישׁ־דָּמִים</p>
<p>⁶ You destroy those who speak falsehood; The LORD abhors the man of bloodshed and deceit.</p>	<p>וּמְרִמָּה יִתְעַב אִיהוָה : ⁸ וְאֲנִי בְּרַב חֶסֶדְךָ אֶבּוֹא בֵיתְךָ אֲשַׁתְּחִנָּה אֶל־</p>
<p>⁷ But as for me, by Your abundant lovingkindness I will enter Your house, At Your holy temple I will bow in reverence for You.</p>	<p>הַיְכָל־קֹדְשֶׁךָ בֵּיתְךָ אֶתְחַנֵּן : ⁹ אִיהוָה אֲנִי נִהְיִי בְּצִדְקָתְךָ לְמַעַן שׁוּרְרֵי הַיֹּשֶׁר [הַיִּשְׂרָאֵל] לְפָנַי דַּרְכְּךָ : ¹⁰ כִּי אֵין בְּפִיָּהוּ נִכּוֹנָה קִרְבָּם תְּנוֹת קִבְר־</p>
<p>⁸ O LORD, lead me in Your righteousness because of my foes; Make Your way straight before me.</p>	<p>פְּתוּת גְּרוֹנָם לְשׁוֹנָם יַחֲלִיקוּן : ¹¹ הָאֲשִׁימָם אֱלֹהִים יִפְלוּ מִמַּעַצְוֹתֵיהֶם בְּרַב פִּשְׁעֵיהֶם</p>
<p>⁹ There is nothing reliable in what they say; Their inward part is destruction <i>itself</i>. Their throat is an open grave; They flatter with their tongue.</p>	<p>הִדְיִחְמוּ כִּי־מָרוּ בָךְ : ¹² וַיִּשְׁמְחוּ כָל־חֹסֵי בָךְ לְעוֹלָם יִרְנְנוּ וְתִסַּךְ עֲלֵימוֹ וַיַּעֲלֶצּוּ בָךְ אֲהַבֵּי שְׂמֶךָ : ¹³ כִּי־אֲתָה תִבְרַךְ צְדִיק יְהוָה כִּצְנֹה רָצוֹן תַּעֲטֶרְנוּ :</p>
<p>¹⁰ Hold them guilty, O God; By their own devices let them fall! In the multitude of their transgressions thrust them out, For they are rebellious against You.</p>	<p>הִיכָל־קֹדְשֶׁךָ בֵּיתְךָ אֶתְחַנֵּן : ⁹ אִיהוָה אֲנִי נִהְיִי בְּצִדְקָתְךָ לְמַעַן שׁוּרְרֵי הַיֹּשֶׁר [הַיִּשְׂרָאֵל] לְפָנַי דַּרְכְּךָ : ¹⁰ כִּי אֵין בְּפִיָּהוּ נִכּוֹנָה קִרְבָּם תְּנוֹת קִבְר־</p>

¹¹ But let all who take refuge in You be glad, Let them ever sing for joy; And may You shelter them, That those who love Your name may exult in You.

¹² For it is You who blesses the righteous man, O LORD, You surround him with favor as with a shield.

Targum

Psa. 5:1 For praise, with dancing. A hymn of David. ² Hear my utterance, O LORD, consider my murmuring. ³ Hear the sound of my petition, my king and God, for I will pray in your presence. ⁴ O LORD, in the morning hear my voice; in the morning I set myself before you and keep watch. ⁵ Because you are not a God who takes pleasure in wickedness; evil did not abide with you. ⁶ Scoffers shall not stand before your eyes; you hate all deeds of falsehood. ⁷ You will destroy tellers of lies; the LORD will loath the man who sheds innocent blood and the deceiver. ⁸ And I, through your great goodness, will enter your house; I will bow down to your temple in awe of you. ⁹ O LORD, guide me by your righteousness; because of my hymn, make firm your paths before me. ¹⁰ Because there is no reliability in the mouths of the wicked; their bodies are full of tumult; like Sheol, their throat is open; their tongues flatter. ¹¹ God has accused them; they will be done away with by their counsel; for their great sin he overturned them, for they rebelled against your command. ¹² And all who trust in your word will rejoice forever; they will give praise and you will protect them; and those who love your name will rejoice in you. ¹³ Because you will bless the righteous, O LORD; as with a shield, you will crown him with good will.

Interlinear

Psa. 5:0 For the choir director for flute accompaniment

Lex
Lex Trl

A Psalm of David

Psa. 5:1 Give ear to my words

Lex אָזַן אָזַן אָמַר
Lex Trl ṣazan ṣazan ṣemer

O Lord Consider my groaning

יהוה בִּין הָגִיג
yhwh bin hagig

Psa. 5:2 Heed the sound of my cry for help

Lex קָשַׁב קוֹל שׁוֹעַ שׁוֹעַ
Lex Trl qashav qol shwᶜ shewaᶜ

my King and my God For to You I

מֶלֶךְ אֱלֹהִים
melekh ṗelohim

pray
פָּלַל
palal

Psa. 5:3 In the morning O Lord You will

Lex בֹּקֵר יהוה
Lex Trl boqer yhwh

hear my voice In the morning I will order my

שָׁמַע קוֹל בֹּקֵר אָרַךְ
shamaᶜ qol boqer ᶜarakh

prayer to You and eagerly watch

צָפָה
tzafah

Psa. 5:4 For You are not a God who takes
 Lex אֵל el chafetz
 Lex Trl

pleasure in wickedness No evil
 חָפֶצֶץ רָשָׁע לֹא רָע
 chafetz resha' lo' ra'

dwells with You
 גִּיר גִּיר
 gur

Psa. 5:5 The boastful shall not stand before Your
 Lex הָלַל יָצַב נִגַּד
 Lex Trl halal yatzav neged

eyes You hate all who do iniquity
 עֵינַי שָׂנֵא כָּל אֲשֶׁר יַעֲשֶׂה אָוֵן
 'ayin sane' kol pa'al 'awen

Psa. 5:6 You destroy those who speak falsehood
 Lex אָבַד דָּבַר כָּזָב
 Lex Trl 'avad davar kazav

The Lord abhors the man of bloodshed and
 יהוה תִּעַב אִישׁ דָּם
 yhwh ta'av 'ish dam

deceit
 מִרְמָה
 mirmah

Psa. 5:7 But as for me by Your abundant lovingkindness I will
 Lex רַב חֶסֶד
 Lex Trl rov chesed

enter Your house At Your holy temple I
 בֹּא בַּיִת אֶת אֶתֶּלֶק הַיְּכָל
 bo' bayit qodesh hekhal

will bow in reverence for You
 שָׁחָה יִרְאַה
 sha'ha yira'

	shachah		yir'ah				
Psa. 5:8	O	Lord	lead	me	in		
Lex		יהוה	נָחָה				
Lex Trl		yhwh	nachah				
Your	righteousness	because	of	my	foes		
	צְדָקָה	מֵעַן			שׂוֹרֵר		
	tzedaqah	ma'an			shorer		
Make	Your	way	straight	before	me		
יָשָׁר		דֶּרֶךְ	יָשָׁר	פָּנִים			
yashar		derekh	yashar	panim			
Psa. 5:9	There	is	nothing	reliable	in	what	they
Lex	אֵין		אֵין	כּוֹן		פֶּה	
Lex Trl	'ayin		'ayin	kun		peh	
say	Their	inward	part	is	destruction	itself	
פֶּה		קֶרֶב	קֶרֶב		הַוָּה		
peh		qerev	qerev		hawwah		
Their	throat	is	an	open	grave	They	
	גָּרוֹן			פֶּתַח	קֶבֶר		
	garon			patach	qever		
flatter	with	their	tongue				
חָלַק			לְשׁוֹן				
chalaq			lashon				
Psa. 5:10	Hold	them	guilty	O	God		
Lex	אָשָׁם		אָשָׁם		אֱלֹהִים		
Lex Trl	'asham		'asham		'elohim		
By	their	own	devices	let	them	fall	In
			מוֹעֲצָה			נָפַל	
			mo'etzah			nafal	
the	multitude	of	their	transgressions	thrust	them	out
	רַב			פְּשָׁע	נָדַח		
	rov			pesha'	nadach		

For they are rebellious against You

מָרָה
marah

Psa. 5:11 But let all who take refuge in You

Lex
Lex Trl

כָּל
kol

חָסָה
chasah

חָסָה
chasah

be glad Let them ever sing for joy
שָׂמַח עוֹלָם רָנַן רָנַן
samach 'olam ranan ranan

And may You shelter them That those

סָכַחַ
sakhakh

who love Your name may exult in You

אָהַב
'ahav

שֵׁם
shem

עָלַץ
'alatz

Psa. 5:12 For it is You who blesses the righteous man

Lex
Lex Trl

בָּרַךְ
barakh

צַדִּיק
tzaddiq

צַדִּיק
tzaddiq

O Lord You surround him with favor as

יְהוָה
yhwh

עָטַר
'atar

רָצוֹן
ratzon

with a shield
צִנָּה
tzinnah

Superscript

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
0 For the choir director; for flute accompaniment. A Psalm of David.	לְמִנְצַחַת אֱלֹהֵי-הַנְּחִילוֹת מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד :

Verse Analysis

This Psalm describes the causes of the revolt that Absalom and his friends held against King David. The main target of the Psalm is Achitophel, whose crimes surpassed that of the people. Achitophel took the most authentic Jewish concepts, the Holy Torah itself, and grotesquely distorted it to serve his own ambitions. He was only interested in material gains in the material world. He yearned for power, honor, and riches.

Achitophel did not view the Torah as an inheritance from the LORD. He was not proud to receive the Torah from his teachers, so his Torah was not genuine.

The Psalm was dedicated to condemning the insincere.

אֱלֹהֵי-הַנְּחִילוֹת (el – han'cheelot) – denotes an inheritance and also the maintenance of spiritual values that are to be preserved forever. It also denotes the final achievements attained by humans on Earth through loyalty – or disloyalty to the LORD. The LORD assigns righteousness to good people. The LORD does not assign anything to wicked people.

The Sage Radak said that **הַנְּחִילֹת** literally means "a swarm of bees" because this word is the name of a musical instrument because it makes a droning bee sound.

The Psalm was dedicated when King David was under attack. The droning buzzing sound captured the mood of the enemy hordes who swarmed around Israel like angry buzzing bees.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The sound of the Nechilos tells us about achieving life's goals, a Psalm of David.

Verse One and Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
¹ Give ear to my words, O LORD, Consider my groaning.	אָמַרְי הֶאֱזִינָה אִיהוָה בִּינָה ² :
² Heed the sound of my cry for help, my King and my God, For to You I pray.	הִגִּינִי הִקְשִׁיבָה אֶל־קוֹל שׁוֹעֵי מֶלֶכִּי ³ וְאֵל־הוֹי כִּי־אֶלֶיךָ אֶתְפַּלֵּל :

Verse Analysis

אָמַרְי (amara) – means "words." This word denotes those thoughts that have already become clear enough to be expressed in words. The Sage Rashi said that this means that when David could express his wants to the LORD that he hoped the LORD would listen and respond.

הֶאֱזִינָה (haazeenah) – means "to give." It denotes to incline the ear for the reception of hearing one's thoughts. The Sage Rashi said that when David was fearful or worried, he had a difficult time praying to the LORD. When that occurred, David hoped that the LORD would hear his needs and help him.

David beseeched the LORD's nearness for all the impulses from his soul. He desired the LORD's presence in his speech, his thinking, and his prayers.

הִקְשִׁיבָה (hak' wheevah) – means "to heed." This word denotes a more intensive form of listening.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

1 Hear my wants, oh LORD, mainly when I cannot express them myself.

2 Listen deeply to my words my LORD, for I pray to you my deepest thoughts.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>³ In the morning, O LORD, You will hear my voice; In the morning I will order <i>my prayer</i> to You and <i>eagerly</i> watch.</p>	<p>יְהוָה בֶּקֶר תִּשְׁמַע קוֹלִי בֶּקֶר אֶעֱרֹךְ-לִי וְאֶצְפָּה :</p>

Verse Analysis

בֶּקֶר (bokar) – means "morning, dawn." Linked with the root בִּקַּר, בֶּקֶר denotes the breaking through of the daylight and thus dawn or, more usually, morning. This noun is peculiar to Hebrew though the assumed root is not. In the first part of the verse, this word intends to denote a time of day. The second time the word occurs, it is meant to indicate the dawning of a new day in the history of humankind.

A period of disaster is always referred to as "night," the dawning of salvation is described in the allegorical simile of "morning" or "dawn."

The LORD's justice (Gevurah) will hand out the final and fitting fate to the righteous and the wicked, each according to his/her merits. This plainly shows to the world the distinction between the righteous and the wicked.

David talked about a time when righteousness and fear of the LORD will reign supreme on the Earth. It will be a bright dawn and cloudless morning. David liked to pray in the early morning. Praying in the morning is good because the requirements of the day have

not consumed all of one's time. David said that he did not precede his prayers with his own personal pursuits.

וַאֲזַעְהוּ (vaatzageh) – means "to watch." The Sage Rashi said that this denotes that David anticipated the punishment for the wicked.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD in the morning, I pray you can hear my voice as I prepare myself for you, and I anticipate your justice on the righteous and wicked.

Verse Four, Five, and Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁴ For You are not a God who takes pleasure in wickedness; No evil dwells with You.</p> <p>⁵ The boastful shall not stand before Your eyes; You hate all who do iniquity.</p> <p>⁶ You destroy those who speak falsehood; The LORD abhors the man of bloodshed and deceit.</p>	<p>כִּי לֹא אֱלֹהִים חֲפִיץ רָשָׁע אֶתְהָה⁵</p> <p>לֹא־יִתְיַצְּבוּ⁶ לֹא יִגְדֹּךָ רָע :</p> <p>הוֹלֵלִים לְגִגֵּד עֵינֶיךָ שְׁנֵאתָ כָּל־</p> <p>תְּאַבְדֵּן דְּבָרֵי כָזָב זִפְעֵלֵי אָוֶן :</p> <p>אִישׁ־דָּמִים וּמְרֻמָּה יִתְעַב יְהוָה :</p>

Verse Analysis

The gloom of the night has covered the history of humanity and society. In a lawless society, evil prevails. Men and women who do violence, who misuse their power, seem to reap tribute and goodwill everywhere. Some people seek to attain their goals, not by means of truth and uprightness but by deceit. The LORD will not allow a wicked person to have a permanent place in this world nor the world to come.

The LORD is a God of righteousness and truth. Deceit is as hateful to the LORD, as is murder. Where there is Godliness, there can be no evil.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

⁴ You are not a God who takes pleasure in wickedness; wherever your Godliness is, evil cannot exist.

⁵ The boastful shall not stand before Your eyes; You hate all who are deceitful.

⁶ You destroy those who speak falsehood; The LORD abhors the man of bloodshed and deceit.

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁷ But as for me, by Your abundant lovingkindness I will enter Your house, At Your holy temple I will bow in reverence for You.</p>	<p>וְאֲנִי בְּרַב חַסְדֶּיךָ אֲבֹא בֵיתְךָ אֲשַׁתְּתֶנָּה אֶל-הַיְכָל-קֹדְשֶׁךָ בִּירְאָתְךָ :</p>

Verse Analysis

There is no future for evil or wicked people. David had to suffer at the hands of deceitful men, particularly by the hands of Achitophel. Achitophel was well skilled in the art of deceit. David being Jewish, was privileged to partake in all gifts from the LORD.

The sanctuary allowed the LORD to teach people how to fashion their lives on Earth so that His Presence will dwell among them even in dark days. David entered the LORD's Temple to thank the LORD for the kindness the LORD heaped upon him by showing David that revenge had been taken upon his enemies.

When David says "your house" and "Holy Sanctuary" he meant the Holy of Holies, the resting place of the Holy Ark.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Nevertheless, as for me, because of your abundant kindness, LORD, I want to enter your Holy Sanctuary.

Verse Eight

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
8 O LORD, lead me in Your righteousness because of my foes; Make Your way straight before me.	9 יְהוָה אֱנִיחֵנִי בְצַדִּיקוֹתֶיךָ לְמַעַן שׁוּרְרֵי הַיָּשָׁר [הַיָּשָׁר] לְפָנַי יִרְכָּךְ :

Verse Analysis

נִחֵנִי (n'chaine) – means "to lead or guide." David asked for help from the LORD that he would be able to recognize the right path and not miss it. David needed the LORD to place the right path before him. David always relied on the LORD; thus, it was not David's decision to determine the right path. The LORD determined David's correct path in life.

A person must do a significant part of the work in the effort of discerning what is right. David's enemies watched him in the hope that he would betray the LORD – then the LORD might desert him.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD help me so I may recognize the right path because my enemies watch over me looking for my failures, place the right path before me.

Verse Nine

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁹ There is nothing reliable in what they say; Their inward part is destruction <i>itself</i>. Their throat is an open grave; They flatter with their tongue.</p>	<p>כִּי אֵין בְּפִיהוּ נְכוּנָה קְרִבָּם ¹⁰ :</p> <p>הַיּוֹת קְבֹר-פִּתּוּחַ גְּרוֹנָם לְשׁוֹנָם</p> <p>יַחֲלִיקוּן :</p>

Verse Analysis

יַחֲלִיקוּן (yachaleekon) – means "to flatter." David was referring to the scheming minds of his enemies. Their throats were an open portal for Sheol. They coated their tongues with such smooth words that anyone who put their trust in them was hopelessly doomed to fall into the grave dug by those plotters of evil.

David was careful because his enemies were always watching him. They were waiting for any errors by David to attack him.

קְבֹר-פִּתּוּחַ גְּרוֹנָם (kaevaer gatoocha g' ronam) – means "open grave throat." The Sage Rashi said David's enemies sought to swallow the fruits of other people's labors, just as an open grave takes in the corpse

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Their spirit is looking for ways to destroy me, they seek to swallow the fruits of other people like the open grave takes in the corpse.

Verse Ten

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁰ Hold them guilty, O God; By their own devices let them fall! In the multitude of their transgressions thrust them out, For they are rebellious against You.</p>	<p>הַאֲשֵׁימָם אֱלֹהִים יִפְּלוּ¹¹ : מִמְעַצְוֹתֵיהֶם בְּרַב פְּשָׁעֵיהֶם תְּדִיתָמוּ כִּי־גָּמְרוּ בָךְ :</p>

Verse Analysis

הַאֲשֵׁימָם (haasheemaym) – means "guilty." This word denotes the destruction which the sinner has brought upon himself. It usually refers to that downfall, which comes as a result of crimes committed against society.

David wanted his enemies sent away because of the multitude of their crimes, and they should lose all the prosperity which they possessed or might yet amass.

David asked the LORD to bring his enemies to justice (Gevurah) and convict them of their guilt and cast them down from their positions of eminence.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

May Gevurah act upon them because of their ways, for their many sins Gevurah must cast them away.

Verse Eleven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹¹ But let all who take refuge in You be glad, Let them ever sing for joy; And may You shelter them, That those who love Your name may exult in You.</p>	<p>וַיִּשְׂמְחוּ כָּל-הַיּוֹסִי בָךְ לְעוֹלָם וַיִּרְנְנוּ וְתַסֵּךְ עָלֵינוּ וַיַּעֲלֵצוּ בָךְ אֱהָבֵי שִׁמְךָ :</p>

Verse Analysis

וַיִּשְׂמְחוּ (v'yees' m'chu) means “to rejoice.” David said that the fall of his adversaries and their destruction was brought upon by themselves. It was through their criminal scheming their destruction came. Justice (Gevurah) dealt with them.

David said that by destroying his enemies, the LORD gave shelter to all those who are threatened by foes.

In David’s era, darkness was occurring because of human sins. An unshakable trust in the LORD’s name reveals His ways and purpose. That trust upholds persons who are faithful to their deity and the LORD’s law and can keep them sure of the dawn in humankind’s history that must come one day.

The Sage Rashi said “You topple the wicked all who trust in you will be glad.”

Joy should be in the LORD and not material things.

וַיִּעֲלֶצוּ (v'ya'ltzoo) means “to exult or rejoice.” This word is used to describe spiritual not physical joy.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

All who put their trust in You will rejoice with good cheer and LORD You give shelter to all persons who love your Name and shall experience spiritual joy.

Verse Twelve

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
¹² For it is You who blesses the righteous man, O LORD, You surround him with favor as with a shield.	כִּי־אַתָּה הַבְרַךְ לְיָרִיב יְהוָה כַּצִּנֹּה רְצוֹן תַּעֲטֶרְנוּ :

Verse Analysis

Lawless men vainly seek to attain prosperity simply by human shrewdness and force. Righteous men receive blessings from the hands of the LORD. Lawlessness seeks evil – you can only temporarily squelch evil because it will always return.

By elevating the spirit of humans, the LORD helps humans attain a proper discernment between the different methods used in the pursuit of the ultimate goal of humanity and thus makes humans victorious over evil.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD, I know you will bless the righteous surrounding them like a shield.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

0 The sound of the Nechilos tells us about achieving life's goals, a Psalm of David.

1 Hear my wants, oh LORD, mainly when I cannot express them myself.

2 Listen deeply to my words my LORD, for I pray to you my deepest thoughts.

3 LORD in the morning, I pray you can hear my voice as I prepare myself for you, and I anticipate your justice on the righteous and wicked.

4 You are not a God who takes pleasure in wickedness; wherever your Godliness is, evil cannot exist.

5 The boastful shall not stand before Your eyes; You hate all who are deceitful.

6 You destroy those who speak falsehood; The LORD abhors the man of bloodshed and deceit.

7 Nevertheless, as for me, because of your abundant kindness, LORD, I want to enter your Holy Sanctuary.

LORD help me so I may recognize the right path because my enemies watch over me looking for my failures, place the right path before me.

9 Their spirit is looking for ways to destroy me, they seek to swallow the fruits of other people like the open grave takes in the corpse.

10 May Gevurah act upon them because of their ways, for their many sins Gevurah must cast them away.

11 All who put their trust in You will rejoice with good cheer and LORD You give shelter to all persons who love your Name and shall experience spiritual joy.

12 LORD, I know you will bless the righteous surrounding them like a shield.

Appendix

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Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

